

Combined Visualization of Wind Waves and Water Surface Temperature

Roland Rocholz¹, Sven Wanner¹, Uwe Schimpf¹, and Bernd Jähne^{1,2}

¹ *Institute of Environmental Physics, Im Neuenheimer Feld 229, University of Heidelberg, Germany, contact: roland.rocholz@iup.uni-heidelberg.de*

² *Heidelberg Collaboratory for Image Processing (HCI) at the Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing, Speyerer Straße 6, University of Heidelberg, Germany*

Abstract. A combined visualization of wind waves and water surface temperature is gained from synchronized and co-located *active thermography* and *wave slope imaging* at a high frame rate (312 Hz). An interactive rendering tool, *WaveVis*, was developed in order facilitate a direct comparison of the space-time evolution of the waves and the surface temperature distribution. For this the water surface elevation is reconstructed from the wave slope and rendered in perspective with OpenGL[®]. The temperature images are mapped in false color onto that virtual surface. Shading, based on the surface slope, is additionally exploited to make the tiny capillary waves visible even though their amplitudes are much smaller than those of the dominating short-gravity waves. *WaveVis* enables to interactively study many mechanisms of air-sea gas exchange, for instance raindrop impacts, microscale breaking waves, and micro Langmuir circulations.

Key Words: water wave imaging, infrared imagery, microscale breaking, visualization

1. Introduction

The exchange rates for heat, gases or momentum at the air-sea interface are controlled by very thin boundary layers (20-2000 μm) (Jähne and Haußecker (1998)). The thickness of these boundary layers is strongly affected by wind waves, surface shear, rain fall and other surface processes that potentially enhance the level of turbulence in the immediate vicinity of the interface. This typically takes place on horizontal scales of millimeters to decimeters and timescales of milliseconds to minutes. The intermittent nature of these processes calls for high spatio-temporal resolution (Jähne et al. (2007)). Much progress was made for the study of isolated processes under certain environmental conditions. But the relative significance of the different processes for a more general range of conditions (e.g. wind, rain, surface slicks) remains unclear. Therefore we aim at measurements that give a broader picture of what happens at the surface.

Imaging techniques are available to accurately measure the temperature of the water surface (thermography) and the shape of the water surface (wave slope imaging). Combining these techniques was shown to be useful for the investigation of microscale breaking waves (e.g. Zappa et al. (2004), Loewen and Siddiqui (2006)) and small scale Langmuir circulations (e.g. Smith et al. (2007), Veron and Melville (2001), Melville et al. (1998)). While the high spatio-temporal resolution of these imaging techniques is generally desirable it also implies the need to handle a huge amount of data for each experiment. For instance, during the WiSSCy experiments (see section 4.) a set of 150 synchronized wave/temperature image sequences were acquired, resulting in roughly 0.5 Tbyte of calibrated data. The huge amount of data is usually handled by choosing a statistical approach, boiling the data down to numbers. In most cases this approach is appropriate to the random nature of the processes. However, the physics behind the observed correlations may become concealed. A close look into the images can aid the interpretation of the results. In many cases, a visual inspection of still images or short sequences sequences is performed using side by side displays (e.g. Zappa et al. (2004)). But the side by side display of image sequences at higher frame rates is not working well for the human perception. An alternative approach is to use color overlays. But displaying the images in different colors on top of each other can be rather misleading.

A more intuitive way to compare the surface temperature distribution to the wave field was sought and is presented in this paper (section 3.). For a direct comparison, the measurements needed to be co-located and synchronized. The corresponding experimental procedure is described in section 2. A few paradigms of the resulting visualization are shown in section 4.

2. Experimental setup and imaging methods

The co-located and synchronized visualization of temperature and waves was gained from a combination of active thermography and wave slope imaging. The apparatus for the active thermography consists of an infrared camera and a scanning CO₂ laser (section 2.2). The wave imaging setup consists of a color camera and a color coded illumination (section 2.1) and is referred to as *Color Imaging Slope Gauge* (CISG). The combined system was set up at the linear wind-wave tank in Hamburg, Germany, during the 2007 WiSSCy-Experiments¹. The infrared camera, the CO₂ laser scanner and the wave imaging camera were mounted 4.5 m above the water surface inside the rain tower section, see figure 1 **a**). The cameras were triggered externally with a custom made electronic circuit at a frequency of 312.5 Hz. The laser scanner was controlled by the same device and operating at a frequency of 19.53 Hz. The imaging sectors of both cameras were overlapping as sketched in figure 2 **a**), with the IR-image enclosing the CISG image. This allows for a geometrical registration of the temperature data to the wave data (section 2.3). The scanning region of the laser was variable for different modes of operation (section 2.2).

2.1 Wave imaging

Small scale features of the wave field can be conveniently measured by means of optical imaging of the gradient \mathbf{s} of the water surface elevation h

$$[\partial_x, \partial_y]^T h(\mathbf{x}) \equiv \mathbf{s} = [s_x, s_y]^T = \tan \alpha [\cos \phi, \sin \phi]^T. \quad (1)$$

Here, α is the inclination of the surface normal relative to the vertical (figure 1 **b**), and ϕ is the polar orientation of the surface normal. Both components of the gradient field were measured simultaneously using the CISG method (Zhang and Cox (1994); Balschbach et al. (1998); Rocholz (2008)). For the CISG setup, a color camera (Pike032c, Allied Vision) is mounted in the air space of the wind wave tank and is looking through the water body onto a color coded illumination below the tank, see figure 1**a**). The observed position on the illumination screen changes with the water surface slope because of the light refraction at the wavy surface as sketched in figure 1**b**). There is a Fresnel lens in focal distance to illumination screen, so that the color to slope relationship is independent from the horizontal coordinates and the depth of the water body. The actual slope to color relationship was determined by a calibration routine, which readily compensates for nonlinearities of the optics and the color coding

¹WiSSCy stands for *Impact of Wind, Rain, and Surface Slicks on Air-Sea CO₂ Transfer Velocity - Tank Experiments*. A cooperation with the Remote Sensing Group of Prof. D. Stammer at the Institute of Oceanography, University of Hamburg.

Figure 1. **a)** Setup in the rain tower section at a fetch of 15 m. **b)** Ray geometry for the slope imaging.

Figure 2. **a)** Sketch of the overlapping imaging sectors and the scanning region of the CO₂ laser. **b)** Registered overlay of the checkerboard images (top) and the scheme for the perspective transformation (bottom).

(Rocholz (2008)). The image size is $223 \text{ mm} \times 104 \text{ mm}$ with 640×298 pixels in along wind and cross wind direction for the color images and 320×149 pixels for the calibrated s_x and s_y images. The effective resolution of the slope images is 0.7 mm per pixel, with a standard deviation of noise of $\sigma_s < 0.03$ and systematic errors of at most 0.1 for slope values in the range ± 1 .

2.2 Active thermography

Using active thermography, i.e. an infrared camera in combination with a CO_2 laser to heat up the water surface, allows to locally measure the heat transfer velocity (Jähne et al. (1989)). In contrast, here we apply active thermography in a different way. To a first approximation, the heat is regarded as a passive tracer. The scanning CO_2 laser is used to prescribe a thermal pattern on the water surface, i.e. the concentration that is monitored by the infrared camera.

The laser power is absorbed at the very surface, with a penetration depth of $11 \mu\text{m}$. The IR camera (CMT 256HS, Thermosensorik) is sensitive to thermal radiation in the 3.4 to $5.1 \mu\text{m}$ range and thus possesses an effective penetration depth of $12 \mu\text{m}$, which is much smaller than the typical thickness of the thermal boundary layer (1000 to $2000 \mu\text{m}$). In contrast to open ocean applications of thermography, we did not have a *cool skin* case (Saunders (1967)) in our experiments. This is because the latent heat flux is zero in the closed wind wave facility (100% humidity). For this, passive thermography was not suitable (Schimpf et al. (2004)). The water bulk and the air space in the wave tank were in thermal equilibrium so that the net radiative transfer was negligible². Therefore and to the first order, the deposited heat could be regarded as a passive proxy tracer to study the diffusive and turbulent transport processes across the surface microlayer.

The spatial resolution of the infrared image is 1.8 mm per pixel. The temperature calibration of the camera is performed with the aid of a blackbody (2004G Santa Barbara Infrared) and involves a correction of the sensor non-uniformity. The noise level for the temperature measurement is $\sigma_T = 18 \text{ mK}$.

The laser beam was widened in cross wind direction via optics and was scanned in along wind direction by a scanning mirror. Different modes for the scanning were used. In the *Area Mode* the laser was continuously scanning over the entire image section. This is useful to visualize surface renewal events, i.e. primarily vertical transport. In the *Line Mode* the laser was continuously

²A water surface layer of $10 \mu\text{m}$ depth that is heated up from 300 K to 301 K would need approximately 7 s to release the thermal energy via radiation. This is much longer than the time scales we are looking at.

scanning within a narrow region³ at the windward boarder of the wave imaging section. This mode is more adequate to visualize of horizontal transport, since this transport is directly apparent from the distortion of the laser line.

2.3 Geometrical registration

A checkerboard target made of copper and plastic (that is visible in the IR images as well as in the color images) was used to determine the perspective transformation of the IR-image to the CISG-image domain, see figure 2**b**). This target was fixed at the mean water level for the acquisition of calibration images. In both calibration images the grid points of the checker-board pattern were extracted with subpixel accuracy, using the geometric camera calibration toolbox by Jean-Yves Bouguet (2008). Then the grid point coordinates were used as controll points for the MatlabTM function `cp2tform`, yielding the perspective transformation matrix. Based on this transformation matrix the corner coordinates (points 1,2,3,4 in figure 2 **b**) of the CISG image in the IR image domain were computed. For the actual interpolation of the IR images the Heurisko[®] function `TransformPerspectiveByPoints` with cubic bi-spline interpolation was used. Ultimately, the registration procedure yields IR images with the same number of pixels and the same spatial discretization as the CISG images, whereas the actual resolution is still in the order of 1.8 mm at the water surface.

2.4 Height reconstruction

The surface elevation (or height) $h(\mathbf{x})$ can be obtained from the surface gradient field $\mathbf{s} = [s_x, s_y]^T = [\partial_x, \partial_y]^T h$ via integration in the Fourier domain using the scheme of Frankot and Chellappa (1988):

$$\hat{h}(\mathbf{k}) = \left(\frac{k_x \hat{s}_x(\mathbf{k}) + k_y \hat{s}_y(\mathbf{k})}{ik^2} \right). \quad (2)$$

Here \hat{h} is the wavenumber spectrum of the surface elevation, \hat{s}_x and \hat{s}_y are the spectra of the surface slope images, $\mathbf{k} = [k_x, k_y]^T$ and k^2 are the wavenumber vector and its squared magnitude, and i is the square root of one. This integration scheme was already applied to wave slope data by Zhang and Cox (1994) and Zhang (1996). It is very efficient and sufficiently accurate for our purpose (Rocholz (2008)). The integration scheme is implemented using the Discrete Fourier transform. Minor artifacts occur at the image borders, because the discrete Fourier Transform implies periodicity at the image boundaries. Due to

³width of the laser line: approx. 1 cm

the division by k^2 in (2) the mean surface elevation $\langle h \rangle$ and the mean surface gradient $[\langle s_x \rangle, \langle s_y \rangle]^T$ are omitted in the integration scheme. The mean surface gradient can be recovered from the mean values of the slope images by adding a corresponding plane to the solution from the inverse Fourier transform of (2)

$$h(\mathbf{x}) = \text{FT}^{-1} \left(\hat{h}(\mathbf{k}) \right) + \langle s_x \rangle x + \langle s_y \rangle y. \quad (3)$$

The spatial coordinate system $\mathbf{x} = [x, y]^T$ is chosen such that its origin is given by the center of the field of view, which enforces a zero mean of the surface elevation for each image. The remaining unknown integration constant $\langle h \rangle$ is solely depending on wavelengths larger than the field of view, which are accordingly not apparent in the wave visualization.

3. The interactive rendering tool - WaveVis

WaveVis is a custom made rendering tool, based on OpenGL[®]. It was developed in order to facilitate a direct comparison of the space-time evolution of the waves and the surface temperature distribution. The image registration (section 2.3) and height reconstruction (section 2.4) are performed off-line with Heurisko[®]. WaveVis interactively displays the water surface height in perspective and true to scale, but with an arbitrary offset to truncate the depth of the water bulk. Shading, based on the surface gradient data, is exploited to make the tiny capillary waves visible - even though their amplitudes are much smaller than those of the dominating short-gravity waves. The temperature images are mapped in false color onto that virtual surface. The color map is arbitrary and its scale can be re-adjusted at runtime. WaveVis is sufficiently quick to allow for real time rendering on a standard PC. However, in practice a tenfold slower display is more appropriate for the visible inspection.

4. Results and discussion

The experimental data comprises 150 synchronized sequences, covering a wide range of conditions, i.e. a range of wind speeds (2 to 14 m/s), in combination with surface slicks (PME, OLA)⁴ and rain (54 mm/h), at a fixed fetch of 15 m. Each sequence contains 5000 frames, which corresponds to 16 seconds.

The combined temperature and wave image sequences provide insights into a variety of mechanisms affecting the thermal boundary layer at the water surface. Here, only two examples are given to show how WaveVis can help to study

⁴OLA = Oleyl Alcohol; PME = Hexadecanoic Acid Methyl Ester

Figure 3. An example for microscale breaking. The frame numbers are given at the lower left corners of the snapshots. The temperature scale comprises $\bar{T} \pm \sigma_T$. Conditions as indicated. Time step 0.064 s (i.e. 20 frames)

the processes⁵. Further examples can be found in Rocholz (2008).

4.1 Microscale wave breaking

Several snapshots of WaveVis are shown in figure 3, giving an example of surface renewal from a microscale breaking wave. The time step between the snapshots is 0.064 s (i.e. 20 frames apart) and the snapshot sequence covers about two periods of the dominant waves. The thin hot (red) line at the right end of each image is the signature of the scanning CO₂ laser (*Line Mode*). A microbreaking wave enters the field of view at frame 950. Prior to this instant, seven periods of the dominant waves with no significant wave breaking passed through the section. Thus, the temperature distribution in the image before the breaking event is a result of the laser heating and horizontal transport due to the wind induced surface shear flow, and - more pronounced - due to the stokes drift of the previous dominant waves. The turbulent wake of the microscale breaking

⁵The display on paper is limited to a few exemplifying snapshots. Therefore it is suggested to regard the digital version on the CD-ROM which is supplied with the book.

wave shortcuts the transfer resistance of the aqueous boundary layer and mixes the warm water parcels from the surface into the water bulk, see frames 950 to 1030. The turbulent wake can be clearly identified from either the IR images or the dimpled surface structure (Zappa et al. (2004)). As Loewen and Siddiqui (2006) pointed out, it is not accurate to define a simple slope threshold as a criterion for the event detection. However, one can literally see the breaking event in the wave slope/height imagery alone. This is because by eye we can distinguish the directionality of the short gravity-capillary waves (e.g. figure 3 frames 870 to 930) from the disordered topography of the wake (e.g. figure 3 frames 950 to 1030). Any algorithm to detect microbreaking with wave imagery should therefore take these differences in topography into account.

For the WiSSCy data set we can frequently observe that microbreaking waves can influence the thermal signature for up to about three periods⁶ of the dominant waves. This has to be taken into account when deducing the dominant processes responsible for surface renewal events obtained from temporal statistics. A bias can be introduced into these statistics due to the prolonged effect of wave breaking induced turbulence.

4.2 Coherent structures

Using the animated display of the WiSSCy data we can frequently observe thermal streaks appearing on the rear face of the dominant waves⁷. These streaks may be associated with (*micro*) *Langmuir circulation*⁸ (Melville et al. (1998); Smith et al. (2007)). The streaks are thought to originate from coherent vortices orientated parallel to the surface and leading to surface convergence/divergence, i.e. downwelling and upwelling zones which might effectively enhance heat/gas exchange (Hara et al. (2007)). For moderate wind speeds, the structures are modulated by the passing waves and thus do not appear as coherent and pronounced as for low wind speeds.

4.3 Rain drop impacts

Figure 4 displays several snapshots for a rain condition⁹. The wind speed (6 m/s) is comparable to that in figure 3 but the surface roughness is increased by a factor of two due to the ring waves from rain drop impacts. The dominant waves are damped very efficiently by the rain, although the rain section covers

⁶e.g. for 8 m/s windspeed the period of the dominant wave was about 0.42 s.

⁷An example is only included in the digital version of this paper.

⁸Whether the physical mechanism is actually the same as for Langmuir circulation is open to question.

⁹Rain rate: approx. 54 mm/h; Drop diameter: 2.9 mm; Falling height 4.5 m; reaching approximately 90% of their terminal velocity.

Figure 4. Rain drop impacts. Time step: 0.0064 s, i.e. 2 frames. The temperature scale comprises $\bar{T} \pm 3 \cdot \sigma_T$

only about 10% of the fetch up to the imaging section. The drops are cold compared to the water surface and can therefore easily be identified as blue dots in the temperature overlays in figure 4¹⁰. The CO₂ laser is operating in *Area Mode* to enhance the contrast in the whole image. With WaveVis we can study the rain drop impacts in some detail and follow their evolution in time. The rain drop craters need about 7 to 10 frames (0.022 s - 0.035 s) to obtain their full size of approximately 2 cm. It takes another 5 to 8 frames for the crater to collapse, emitting the first ring waves at this stage. About 40-50 frames later, the rain impact can no longer be identified in the IR images. Thus, it takes approximately 0.2 s for thermal boundary layer to recover from the impact.

5. Conclusion and outlook

WaveVis is a very useful tool for the interpretation of thermographic imagery (or other kind of water surface concentration or flow fields) with respect to the wind driven waves. The wave and temperature information is combined very intuitively for an interactive computer animation. This opens new pos-

¹⁰In the IR image a rain drop is actually already visible before it hits the surface, but due to the focusing of the camera one can see only drops that are close to the water surface.

sibilities to literally observe air-sea interaction processes that otherwise may remain concealed, somewhere within correlation plots or Tbytes of raw data. Conversely, the significance of wave breaking and wave-wave interaction for the gas/heat exchange can be studied.

Microscale breaking is reckoned to have a significant influence on the air-sea exchange. The detection of microscale breaking with thermography works very well, but only as long as the temperature difference between the water surface and water bulk is sufficiently high. This is either in the cool skin case or using active themography. The wakes of microscale breaking waves can also be identified in the wave imagery as dimpled areas which always coincide with surface renewal as seen with the aid of WaveVis in the temperature overlay. An algorithm to detect the turbulent wake, based on wave slope/height data only, is currently under development.

The influence of rain on gas exchange is certainly complicated by the interplay of wind driven waves, rain induced subsurface turbulence, and the additional surface roughness due to impact craters and ring waves. As briefly demonstrated, the combined visualization of waves and water surface temperature provides a promising way to shed light upon that subject.

Acknowledgments We gratefully acknowledge the funding for the WiSSCy-Project that was provided by the German Research Foundation (DFG) under contracts JA-395/13 and STA-410/5-2. Special thanks to Dr. Christoph Garbe (HCI, Uni Heidelberg, Germany), Dr. Susanne Krömker (IWR, Uni Heidelberg, Germany) and Michael Jung (IWR, Uni Heidelberg, Germany) for their contribution in the initial stage of the development of WaveVis.

References

- Balschbach, G., J. Klinke, and B. Jähne (1998), Multichannel shape from shading techniques for moving specular surfaces, in *Computer Vision - ECCV'98*, Springer, Berlin.
- Bouguet, J.-Y. (2008), Camera calibration toolbox for matlab, http://www.vision.caltech.edu/bouguetj/calib_doc/.
- Frankot, R. T. and R. Chellappa (1988), A method for enforcing integrability in shape from shading algorithms, *IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell.*, 10(4), 439–451.
- Hara, T., E. VanInwegen, J. Wendelbo, C. S. Garbe, U. Schimpf, B. Jähne, and N. Frew (2007), Estimation of air-sea gas and heat fluxes from infrared imagery based on near surface turbulence models, in C. S. Garbe, R. A. Handler, and B. Jähne (Eds.), *Transport at the Air Sea Interface*, Springer-Verlag.

- Jähne, B. and H. Haußecker (1998), Air-water gas exchange, *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, *30*, 443–468.
- Jähne, B., P. Libner, R. Fischer, T. Billen, and E. J. Plate (1989), Investigating the transfer process across the free aqueous boundary layer by the controlled flux method, *Tellus*, *41B*(2), 177–195.
- Jähne, B., C. Popp, U. Schimpf, and C. Garbe (2007), The influence of intermittency on air/water gas transfer measurements, in C. S. Garbe, R. A. Handler, and B. Jähne (Eds.), *Transport at the Air Sea Interface*, Springer-Verlag.
- Loewen, M. R. and M. H. Kamran Siddiqui (2006), Detecting microscale breaking waves, *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, *17*, 771–780.
- Melville, W. K., R. Shear, and F. Veron (1998), Laboratory measurements of the generation and evolution of langmuir circulations, *J. Fluid Mech.*, *364*, 31–58.
- Rocholz, R. (2008), *Spatiotemporal Measurement of Short Wind-Driven Water Waves*, Dissertation, Institute of Environmental Physics, Faculty of Physics and Astronomy, Univ. Heidelberg. http://hci.iwr.uni-heidelberg.de/publications/dip/2008/Rocholz_2008_Diss.pdf
- Saunders, P. M. (1967), The temperature at the ocean-air interface, *J. Atmos. Sci.*, *24*(3), 269–273.
- Schimpf, U., C. Garbe, and B. Jähne (2004), Investigation of transport processes across the sea surface microlayer by infrared imagery, *J. Geophys. Res.*, *109*(C8), C08S13.
- Smith, G. B., R. A. Handler, and N. Scott (2007), Observations of the structure of the surface temperature field at an air-water interface for stable and unstable cases, in C. S. Garbe, R. A. Handler, and B. Jähne (Eds.), *Transport at the Air Sea Interface*, Springer-Verlag.
- Veron, F. and W. K. Melville (2001), Experiments on the stability and transition of wind-driven water surfaces, *J. Fluid Mech.*, *446*, 25–65.
- Zappa, C. J., W. E. Asher, A. T. Jessup, J. Klinke, and S. R. Long (2004), Micro-breaking and the enhancement of air-water transfer velocity, *J. Geophys. Res.*, *109*, C08S16.
- Zhang, X. (1996), An algorithm for calculating water surface elevations from surface gradient, *Exp. Fluids*, *21*, 43–48.
- Zhang, X. and C. S. Cox (1994), Measuring the two-dimensional structure of a wavy water surface optically: A surface gradient detector, *Exp. Fluids*, *17*, 225–237.